

COMPARATIVE FREQUENCY OF PREVALENCE OF VARIOUS FORMS OF CAPITALA HYPOSPADIAS IN CHILDREN OF ANDIZHAN

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Relevance. Hypospadias as a disease was first described by Galen. However, hypospadias remains the most important medical and medical - social problem today throughout the world.

The medical and social significance of hypospadias is due to its high prevalence, the tendency to a constant increase in the number of patients - children, high disability due to complications and great economic damage.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the issues of epidemiology and prevention of hypospadias. This is due to the fact that despite the large number of proposed methods of surgical correction, the treatment of hypospadias still remains one of the most difficult problems in pediatric urology due to the high percentage of complications.

Treatment of hypospadias is not only a complex, but also not fully resolved problem. Therefore, the frequency of births of children with various forms of hypospadias and the high percentage of postoperative complications, which, according to modern researchers, reach 50%, continues to increase.

In this regard, the search for and study of safe and highly effective screening (epidemiological innovative approaches) methods for early pre-nosological prevention and treatment of hypospadias is a pressing problem for medical science and practical healthcare.

The aim of the study: to study the prevalence, improve the effectiveness of prevention and surgical treatment of hypospadias based on our own innovative developments in children of the Fergana Valley.

The object of the study was 914 children with hypospadias from the Fergana Valley (202 in the Andijan region, 467 in the Namangan region and 245 in the Fergana region) aged 0–18 years.

The subjects of the study were venous and capillary blood, urine, analysis of subjective and objective data, assessment of risk factors, materials, digital rectal examination of the prostate gland, data from drug therapy and surgical treatment, as well as endoscopic and urodynamic equipment.

Research methods. To achieve the goal of the dissertation and fulfill the set tasks, subjective, physical, survey, clinical, biochemical, pharmacoepidemiological, instrumental, special (digital rectal, echographic, transrectal ultrasound, uroflowmetric, urethrocystoscopic, surgical) and statistical methods were used.

Results of the study: we studied the comparative aspect of the epidemiological features of the detection of capitate hypospadias (CHH) and its individual clinical forms of OHS, DHS and SSHS in children of the Andijan region of the Fergana Valley. The following levels of prevalence of CHH (n = 113) were established depending on the age of the examined children: 3.54% at 0-1 years, 69.03% at 2-4 years, 23.01% at 5-9 years, 2.65% at 10-14 years and 1.77% at 15-18 years. The frequency of detection in connection with age differs by 68.3%, its highest levels occur in the age groups of 2-4 years and 5-9 years [Chi2 15.507; Df = 8; P < 0.05]. The prevalence rate of OGS in individual age groups of children was: 0.00% in 0-1 years, 2.56% in 2-4 years, 3.85% in 5-9 years, 0.00% in 10-14 years, 0.00% in 15-18 years, and 2.65% in 0-18 years. High prevalence was noted among children aged 5-9 years. Depending on the age of the examined children of Andijan, the frequency of detection of DGS (n = 99) and SSGS (n = 11) were established at the following levels: at 0-1 years 75.00% and 25.00% (P < 0.01), at 2-4 years 91.03% and 6.41% (P < 0.001), at 5-9 years 64.62% and 11.54% (P < 0.001), at 10-14 years 66.67% and 33.33% (P < 0.01), at 15-18 years 50.00% and 50.00%, at 0-18 years 87.61% and 9.73 (P < 0.001), respectively. Relatively high prevalence rates of DGS were found in the age groups of children 2-4 years, 5-9 years, and 0-1 years, and SGS - in 15-18 years, 10-14 years, and 0-1 years.

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